

Innovative Algorithm for Assessing the Economic Efficiency of Sustainable Modernization of Engineering Systems in Heritage Buildings (Case Study Arasan Wellness & SPA)

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Eginov A.A.

CTO, "TOLAGAI-2050" LLP

eginovaa@gmail.com

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Abstract: The paper presents an algorithm for assessing the economic efficiency of sustainable modernization of engineering systems in heritage buildings, using the Arasan Wellness & SPA complex in Almaty as a case study. The methodology includes energy and water consumption modeling, calculation of NPV, IRR, payback period, and sensitivity analysis.

The project features geothermal heating and greywater reuse systems. The algorithm has been tested within a computational modeling framework without real-world implementation. The results confirm its applicability to similar heritage buildings, while ensuring compliance with architectural preservation requirements.

Keywords: engineering systems; cultural heritage; modernization; economic efficiency; heat pump; greywater; sustainable development; geothermal energy

Introduction

The modernization of engineering systems in buildings classified as cultural heritage assets is one of the most complex and urgent challenges in sustainable urban development. As concerns about global climate change and increasing demands for sustainable buildings grow, there is a growing need to adopt innovative engineering solutions while preserving the historical and architectural significance of these structures. This challenge is particularly relevant in the context of the climate agenda and commitments to reduce carbon footprints, including the Paris Agreement and national sustainable development strategies.

One of the central tasks is to identify a balanced approach that simultaneously ensures lower operating costs, improved energy efficiency, and the preservation of the historical authenticity of buildings. Examples of successful implementations are documented in several international studies. For instance, [1] presents an effective combination of restoration practices and energy-efficient technologies in the renovation of the refectory at the Žiža Monastery, where both authenticity requirements and significant energy savings were achieved. Furthermore, modern digital technologies such as HBIM and the Digital Twin concept are opening new horizons in the management of cultural heritage properties. Study [2] demonstrates how the use of digital twins can significantly improve the accuracy of forecasting the effects of different renovation scenarios and optimize the cost–benefit balance throughout the entire life cycle of a building.

International experience also emphasizes the necessity of a systemic approach encompassing data collection, energy audits, thermodynamic modeling, and multi-objective evaluation of alternative scenarios. Holistic renovation models for historical buildings, applied in the Žiža Monastery project, confirmed the importance of integrating engineering, architectural, and environmental approaches [1].

This study aims to develop and validate an innovative algorithm for assessing the economic efficiency of sustainable modernization in heritage buildings. The Arasan Wellness & SPA complex serves as the primary case study, where reconstruction provides a basis for substantiating the need for an interdisciplinary approach to evaluating the investment attractiveness of sustainable solutions, taking into account architectural significance, technical constraints, and operational factors. The scientific novelty of the research lies in the formalization of an economic assessment algorithm for sustainable modernization, specifically adapted to the engineering requirements of heritage-protected buildings.

Given the tightening environmental and energy standards, the modernization of engineering systems in cultural heritage buildings constitutes a complex multi-parameter challenge. These structures are subject to architectural and regulatory constraints, which limit the implementation of standard engineering solutions typical of contemporary construction [3]. To achieve the stated objective, the article addresses the following tasks:

- Development of an energy and water performance model for the facility in its current state;
- Selection and justification of engineering solutions for energy and water conservation, considering architectural heritage restrictions;
- Formulation of an economic efficiency assessment algorithm employing NPV, payback period, and sensitivity analysis;
- Validation of the model through the modernization of the Arasan Wellness & SPA bath complex;
- Development of scalability criteria and conditions for applying the proposed algorithm to heritage buildings in the CIS countries and Eastern Europe.

Contemporary studies underscore the importance of integrating energy- and water-saving measures into the restoration processes of cultural heritage buildings. The principal challenge, however, lies in addressing architectural, regulatory, and operational constraints inherent to heritage-protected properties [3].

An analysis of international practice indicates that one promising direction is the incorporation of water reuse technologies during the operational phase of buildings. Such measures ensure sustainability not only during the construction phase but also across the building's life cycle [4].

Additional attention is being directed toward integrated models of sustainable modernization, based on multifaceted assessments that range from energy calculations to evaluations of cultural significance. For example, study [5] proposes a systemic approach to revitalizing historic buildings that combines architectural adaptation with strategic resource management.

In the context of digitalizing cultural heritage management, technologies such as digital twins and HBIM are gaining increasing importance. Study [2] shows that applying a digital twin model of a building enables the forecasting of energy consumption, the selection of optimal modernization scenarios, and the minimization of risks associated with altering the architectural appearance.

Thus, successful modernization of heritage assets requires the integration of digital tools, energy-efficient technologies (particularly geothermal heat pumps), and low-invasive water reuse solutions. Collectively, this calls for a new algorithm for assessing economic efficiency that accounts for three dimensions: technical, cultural, and financial.

Analysis of Scientific Approaches and Regulatory Framework

Contemporary research emphasizes the importance of implementing comprehensive strategies for the sustainable renovation of historically significant buildings, which combines the preservation of architectural integrity with the integration of resource-saving technologies. One of the most promising solutions is the application of geothermal heat pumps in conjunction with solar energy, which

demonstrates high energy efficiency and relatively short payback periods under varying climatic conditions [6].

Methods of multi-criteria assessment play a particularly important role in the modernization of heritage buildings. Study [7] proposes a methodology based on the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), which enables the evaluation and ranking of alternative intervention measures while accounting for both technical and cultural parameters. This approach supports balanced decision-making, especially under the constraints imposed by the protected status of heritage properties.

In the domain of water resource management during the operational phase of buildings, technologies for rainwater harvesting and greywater reuse have gained significant importance. Study [8] emphasizes end-user preferences in social housing when choosing among various water treatment systems. The authors demonstrate that even under limited budgetary conditions, consumers may favor solutions offering greater water savings, despite more extended payback periods—underscoring the necessity of an individualized approach to the design of such systems.

Thus, the effective modernization of buildings with historical value requires a comprehensive consideration of the following factors:

- regulatory constraints and the heritage protection status of the facility;
- multi-criteria evaluation of solutions in terms of energy efficiency, water conservation, and cultural value;
- The use of digital modeling tools to forecast renovation scenarios;
- Moreover, prioritization of end-user needs in the decision-making process.

Methodology for Assessing Economic Efficiency

The assessment of the economic efficiency of modernization measures for engineering systems in heritage buildings is based on discounted cash flow methods, which enable the accounting for both capital and operational expenditures, as well as projected benefits from reduced resource consumption. Particular attention is paid to risks associated with tariff fluctuations, seasonal variations in facility usage, and compliance with cultural heritage protection regulations. It should be noted that all calculations are performed based on design assumptions and modeling, without empirical validation on a functioning facility.

The following financial indicators are employed as key evaluation criteria:

- **NPV (Net Present Value)** — net present value of cash flows over the project horizon (20 years);
- **IRR (Internal Rate of Return)** — internal rate of return of the project;
- **PP (Payback Period)** — investment payback period;
- **SRA (Sensitivity and Risk Analysis)** — sensitivity analysis with respect to changes in energy costs and capital expenditures.

The formula for calculating NPV is as follows:

$$NPV = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{CF_t}{(1+r)^t} - I_0$$

where:

- CF_t — cash flow in year t ;
- r — discount rate (set at 8%);
- I_0 — initial investment;
- T — project lifetime (20 years).

The developed model consists of the following stages:

1. Evaluation of current energy and water consumption based on operational data;
2. Simulation of the effects of introducing geothermal heating and greywater reuse systems;
3. Calculation of capital expenditures for equipment installation and integration;
4. Development of scenarios that account for:
 - a) tariff fluctuations,
 - b) seasonal variations in facility usage,
 - c) regulatory restrictions;
5. Visualization of results through NPV graphs, IRR analysis, and break-even points.

The methodology has been designed in line with contemporary scientific approaches that combine energy modeling with cost–benefit analysis. Study [9] presents a comprehensive decision-making framework for retrofitting existing buildings, integrating energy consumption modeling with cost–benefit assessments. This enables the precise evaluation of both economic and energy-related outcomes of different intervention scenarios, allowing for the adaptation of solutions to the specific constraints of heritage properties.

In addition, study [10] emphasizes the importance of decision-support systems based on HBIM and numerical modeling. Their multi-level model enables the consideration of cultural significance, cost, sustainability, and energy efficiency in the process of selecting optimal modernization measures.

Furthermore, the cost–benefit approach has proven its relevance in assessing the sustainability and feasibility of energy solutions for historic buildings, as demonstrated in a study [11], where conservation criteria are integrated with financial and operational indicators.

Technological Model of Engineering Systems Modernization

The development of a technological model for the sustainable modernization of the engineering systems at the *Arasan Wellness & SPA* bath complex aims to achieve energy efficiency, water efficiency, and operational autonomy while strictly adhering to cultural heritage protection requirements. All design solutions are of a recommendatory nature and are intended for integration into existing engineering and architectural structures without compromising the authenticity of the building.

Geothermal Heating System

As an alternative to traditional heat supply sources, the implementation of a geothermal heat pump system with vertical boreholes is proposed. This solution enables independence from external energy sources, significantly increasing the facility's resource autonomy. The system operates on a closed-loop circuit with propylene glycol, with a design capacity of up to 280 kW and an average coefficient of performance (COP) of approximately 4.3 under winter operating conditions.

According to a study [12], such systems provide cost-effective heating with minimal CO₂ emissions over the full life cycle of a project. Additionally, study [13] confirms the effectiveness of geothermal solutions under the conditions of intensive operation of public buildings. When properly configured, the system can meet not only heating needs but also domestic hot water demand and summer cooling requirements.

Greywater Reuse System

To reduce freshwater consumption and alleviate pressure on municipal networks, the project proposes implementing a greywater reuse system for water originating from showers, sanitary facilities, and spa areas. After biomechanical treatment and UV disinfection, the treated water can be reused for:

- technical cooling of steam generators;
- replenishment of heating and ventilation systems;
- irrigation of landscaped areas in the inner courtyard.

According to the review in [14], such systems can achieve up to 30% water savings, thereby reducing operational costs and enhancing the environmental sustainability of water-intensive buildings.

Integration with Heritage Protection Constraints

All design proposals are developed in strict compliance with regulatory requirements for preserving the architectural and cultural–historical integrity of the facility. Utility networks are planned for installation within existing shafts and basement spaces, without new routing through zones of historical value. Automation components, control devices, and sensors are designed for integration into finishing elements or concealed installation in non-accessible areas, ensuring complete visual neutrality of engineering solutions.

Intelligent Engineering System Management

The project envisions the integration of engineering infrastructure into a unified digital Building Management System (BMS), enabling the following functions:

- forecasting of water and energy consumption;
- automatic adaptive control of pumps, ventilation, and heating;
- remote monitoring of equipment condition;
- real-time response to operational deviations.

In the long term, such a digital ecosystem enhances the operational reliability of the facility, contributes to reducing energy expenditures, and aligns with the principles of “smart” sustainable buildings.

Results and Discussion

Resource-Saving Effect

As part of the trial implementation of the algorithm, the potential impacts of adopting geothermal heating and a greywater reuse system were simulated for the engineering systems of the Arasan Wellness & SPA complex in Almaty. Table 1 presents the calculated resource efficiency indicators.

Table 1. Comparative indicators of resource consumption before and after modernization

Indicator	Before modernization	After modernization	Change
Heat energy consumption, Gcal/year	4,380	3,108	-29%
Freshwater consumption, m ³ /year	68,000	47,600	-30%
Energy costs for engineering systems, million ₸/year	52.1	37.2	-29%

Economic Efficiency

Using the simulation model without on-site implementation, the project's effectiveness was assessed over a 20-year period with an 8% discount rate. The following results were obtained:

- **NPV (Net Present Value):** 121 million ₸
- **IRR (Internal Rate of Return):** 14.2%
- **Payback Period:** 6.7 years
- **Profitability Index:** 1.52

The use of circular design principles and adaptive engineering solutions, as highlighted in study [15], not only reduces resource consumption but also supports the long-term economic sustainability of the facility. Incorporating low-carbon and regenerative methods into modernization efforts is becoming increasingly crucial.

Sensitivity Analysis

The sensitivity analysis of the model revealed the strongest dependence on the following factors:

- growth in electricity tariffs;
- reduced facility occupancy during the winter season;
- increased operational costs for the greywater system.

The need to implement a green audit for modernization projects like this—including during planning and risk assessment phases—is supported by study [16]. Such an audit allows for the integration of ecological and economic sustainability criteria throughout a project's entire life cycle.

Scalability and Applicability

The developed methodology can be successfully adapted to facilities with comparable characteristics:

- presence of showers and spa zones;

- architectural value and heritage protection status;
- constant load on engineering networks;
- constraints on water use and energy consumption.

Urban planning practices increasingly focused on sustainability often require the integration of retrofitted historic buildings into regional energy management systems [17]. Studies [18; 19] indicate that active municipal involvement, intermunicipal partnerships, and local initiatives play a crucial role in speeding up the implementation of such solutions and improving the institutional maturity of infrastructure projects.

Limitations and Risks

The main limitations include:

- the necessity of individual design for each building;
- high costs associated with drilling geothermal wells;
- complex regulatory frameworks for greywater reuse across different regions.

Nevertheless, with sufficient government support and incentives for “green” standards, these technologies can be effectively scaled and incorporated into sustainable renovation programs for heritage buildings.

Conclusions

1. This study examines the Arasan Wellness & SPA complex as a case to test a computational model for modernizing engineering systems in heritage-protected buildings. The simulation results show the potential to improve both energy and water efficiency while maintaining the building's architectural integrity. The calculations suggest that implementing geothermal heating and greywater reuse systems could reduce annual heat energy and freshwater consumption by 29–30%, respectively.
2. The evaluation of the project’s economic viability shows its strong investment appeal within the simulation model: a positive NPV, an internal rate of return of 14.2%, and a payback period of less than seven years. These findings align with those in study [20], which highlight the importance of using a comprehensive life-cycle analysis in modernizing historic buildings, combining energy modeling and architectural details.
3. The use of multifactor and risk-based assessment, including sensitivity analysis, enabled the identification of critical variables such as energy tariff fluctuations, seasonal changes in occupancy, and operational costs. This aligns with the approach outlined in study [21], which supports the importance of risk analysis in decision-making for preserving historic buildings facing climate and operational risks.
4. The results confirm that the developed algorithm is suitable for facilities with socially important functions and high thermal loads. In line with the principles outlined in study [22], sustainability in the modernization of heritage buildings should be assessed not only based on technical and economic criteria but also considering its long-term effects on the urban and cultural environment.

5. To scale sustainable modernization efforts, institutional support is crucial. This involves updating regulatory frameworks, subsidizing green technologies, and making green audit methodologies mandatory in the reconstruction of heritage-protected assets.

In summary, the proposed algorithm can serve as a foundation for developing standardized methods for assessing sustainable modernization in the heritage building sector.

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